

**ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF COTTON
GROWING IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract. the economic basis for the development of cotton production was formed on the basis of the results of a scientific study on the development and economic efficiency of cotton production in Uzbekistan. Conclusions and proposals have been developed on the development and economic efficiency of cotton growing.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, Cotton, Development, economic efficiency, profitability, cooperative.

Agriculture occupies a significant place in the economy of Uzbekistan. As of the end of 2022, the share of this network in Uzbekistan GDP was 25.1 percent. Cotton, considered one of the leading sectors of Republican Agriculture, occupies an important place not only in the agrarian sector, but also in ensuring the stability of the country's economy.

Research in this area shows that during the Reform years, under the influence of intensive and extensive factors in the development of Republican cotton production, a continuous increase in the volume of production and raw materials of cotton grown at the expense of the resource unit is not achieved. Analysis shows that nearly 1.8 million in the Republic by 1990. Cotton was planted on hectares of land, and farms specializing in cotton cultivation accounted for 75-80% of the total arable land, while today Cotton arable land is 1.04 million. hectares account for 24.8% of total arable land. On the scale of the Republic, cotton arable land was established in 2022 by 19.

**The main indicators of cotton development in the Republic of Uzbekistan in
1991-2021**

Specification	Years							In 2022 1991-per-year, %
	1991	1995	2000	2001	2002	2003	2022	
Total cultivated area, per thousand	4200,3	4165,0	3778,3	3438,4	3475,0	3368,9	4214	100.3
Including cotton arable land, thousand	1720,5	1492,2	1444,6	1450,1	1420,7	1392,7	1046.2	60.8
Cotton crop area share of, %	40,9	35,8	38,2	44,7	40,9	41,3	24.8	-
Cotton production, thousand tons	4645,3	3929,5	3001,9	3270,3	3164,7	2822,0	3400,0	73,2
Productivity, to s /	27,0	26,3	20,8	22,5	22,3	20,3	32.5	120.3

Source: compiled on the basis of data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In the course of this study, we got acquainted with the statistics of the state of cotton cultivation in the Andijan region, where our country is located in 1% of the total land area, but where about 10% of the country's population lives. Looking at the Cotton of the past period in the region, cotton raw materials were produced by companies and farms in 2001. As of 2022, cotton raw materials are grown in the region by cotton–textile clusters and farms. As a result of the economic reforms carried out in the cotton sector in Andijan region, by 2022 cotton dressing was on average 37.0 per hectare in cotton-textile clusters and on average 34.0 centners per hectare in farms. The average yield of cotton crop fields in the region is 20.0-25.0 centners average in cotton in the Republic, while in some regions the average yield of cotton is 12-15 centners in Andijan region this figure averages 34-35 centners.

**Economic efficiency of growing cotton in the Andijan region in
2016-2022**

№	Specification	Unit of measurement	2016	2017	2018	2020	2022
1	Arable land	ga	91400	89200	81791	79391	78991
2	Dressing	s/ga	28.7	26.8	26.5	34	35.4
3	Gross dressing	tonne	261945	239378	216850	268232	279767
4	Total costs	mln.so ' m	262235	479352.5	671268	1128430	1605413
5	Total income	mln.so ' m	287081	445392	705464	1235188	1891564
Average per 1 hectare							
6	Costs	Rs	2869	5373.9	8207	14214	20324
7	Income	Rs	3141	4993.2	8625	15568	23947
Average compared to 1 ton of products							
8	Cost of 1 ton of products	Rs	1001	2002.5	3095.5	4207	5738
9	1 ton product of average sales price	Rs	1096	1860.6	3253.2	4605	6761
10	Profitability	%	9.5	-7.1	5.1	9.5	17.8

Source: data from the Department of Agriculture of Andijan region

As can be seen from the table data, we can see that by 2022, cotton dressing has increased on average to 35.4 centners per hectare, while the profitability rate, which completes economic efficiency, has increased from 9.5 percent in 2016 to 17.8 percent. The fact that the achieved result is not at the level of demand indicates that there are several problems that are relevant to be considered in the field of improving the economic efficiency of cotton growing. In particular, the stagnant and rapid increase in prices for material and technical resources in cotton production has significantly affected it for the past decade to become a harmful sector from economic waste. Today, among the tasks of Agrarian Policy, the task of improving the system of providing cotton farms with material and technical resources has also taken an important place. Therefore, it is necessary to revise the system in force today on the supply of material and technical resources and replace it with a completely new system.

Model Organization of the supply and Service Cooperative structure

The supreme governing body of the cooperative is the general meeting of members. The general meeting is held once a year at the conclusion of the reporting year. A general meeting may be called in turn in accordance with the decision of the Cooperative Council or at the initiative of at least one third of the members. The cooperative Council is elected by the general meeting of farmers entering the co-operative for a term of one year. One of the board members is elected to serve a one-year term as chairman of the board. The council and its chairman operate on a community basis.

The proposed cooperative is fundamentally different from the current system of macalized supply and service, and it is envisaged that this system of supply will be valid in fully liberated conditions, cooperatives will operate strictly following the orders of farmers. Since the cooperative is organized on the basis of the property of farmers, as their organization, it is both responsible and interested in the implementation of work and services on its own term and qualityю

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